

INTERLANGUAGE ERRORS IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AMONG LEARNERS

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Annotation: The level of second language acquisition based on various factors which make the learning process easy or complicated. The present paper deals with Interlanguage difficulties and errors among children and determines overcoming period and circumstances of errors and difficulties. After defining the term and classifying origin and development of interlanguage, a detailed review of the studies: causes and treatments of errors, classification of fossilization open central goals of the study. The paper concludes by emphasizing that interlanguage errors which causes difficulties should be facilitated by teachers and learners with beneficial strategies and ways in order to prevent permanent fossilization of errors even target language learning process of children.

Key words: interlanguage, Interlanguage errors and causes of errors and error treatment, fossilization.

Introduction

There are great amount of research works were carried out regarding Interlanguage (IL) in Second Language Acquisition (SLA) among children all over the world. However this topic has not been achieved piloted aims since lack of research work has been done in this field around Uzbekistan.

Interlanguage differs from first language (L1) and second language (SL) which is counted as a separate linguistic system and second language learning period requests to shape the language by transferring from native language (NL). Similar rules between two languages' natures facilitate learning process but differences lead learners encounter difficulties and errors. In addition, while gradual developments of interlanguage from first language towards second language, learners' errors are observed and this is known natural phenomenon. The occurrence of errors based on various reasons: structural differences between Mother tongue and Target language (TL), wrong conceptions, Learner variables (etc.) and in variety of fields: pronunciation, accents, word use, grammar, and vocabulary etc. Overcoming negative impacts' process gets across variously among children, adolescents and adults according to psychological state. Especially children gain data unconsciously by behaviorism rules and language acquisition device (LAD) because of limit in psychological development and analytical skills. This is why children who are second

language learners (SLLs) achieve high level of facility of using and acquiring TL rather than adults. However, Larry Selinker (1972) explains that regardless of learners' age or total training, a permanent fossilization of IL occurs before learner achieved TL norms at all levels of linguistic structure despite learner's positive ability, motivation to gain the language opportunity and acculturation of target society. The goal of the literature review is to find answer to set question: Do children who are SLLs experience interlanguage difficulties, errors? If so: how long and what circumstances?

Origins of concept of Interlanguage and its development

Tarone (2006) gave the general idea that SLLs' inter-language as a self-standing, distinct system from NL and TL. The notion of interlanguage was put forward by Selinker in 1972 in order to show that learners' learning language as a separate language variety, since it covers distinct rules and representatives (Yang, 2002, Tarone 2006, 2018).

The concept was conceptualized by Nemster as an "approximative system" and "Transitional competence" by Corder. But the notion of interlanguage was used solely in the second-language acquisition literature in 1990 (Tarone, 2006). For the development of the term: IL was no systematic attempts to carry out scientific official papers in 1950 and 1960 because claims were not supported by obtained data instead predictions (Tarone, 2018). Next step was proposed by Robert Lado that error analysis in speech and writing of SLLs can help contrastive analysis predictions and it was first time for moving from teaching materials to second-language learning problems. However errors did not seem to be cause of predictive, contrastive analysis transfer (Lennon, 2003). Eventually the term: interlanguage introduced in persuasive manner which by objectively identifying psycholinguistic processes that helps shaping learner language, gives explanation interlanguage identifications across linguistic system and fossilization period by Selinker, Corder and other scholars (Tarone, 2006)

Defining Interlanguage

Tarone (2006, 2018) claims that interlanguage is a separate linguistic system not only covers phonology, morphology and syntax but also lexical pragmatic and discourse level of the IL and it is thought of adult second-language learners who have passed puberty and can not use language acquisition device (LAD) and children can re-engage LAD. This is why they can avoid ultimate fossilization. Yang (2002) informs that central notion of inter-language is fossilization and it processes mostly among adults because of latent psychological structure which contains SL transfer, overgeneralization of TL rules, transfer of training, communication strategies and learning strategies. The concept situates between mother tongue and target language and improvement occurs when TL input increases rapidly (Yang, 2002).

Interlanguage errors and causes of errors and error treatment

Ellis gives definition for errors which occurs because learners do not have correct answer (Tiarina, 2017). Especially children come across errors because they have lack of comprehension regarding TL and lack of analyzing ability about pronunciation, listening, speaking, reading writing, spelling, grammar and vocabulary which make them to accept with the help of transfer training experience, communication and learning strategies, behaviorism and teachers' teaching strategies and materials. Touchie (1986) claims that human language learning phase involves committing errors. Learners use their knowledge of mother tongue to understand and organize SL and if there are differences between native and second language transferring may lead to make errors and difficulties as well.

For example: If we compare Russian with Uzbek, Uzbek language does not demonstrate gender (Russian он она) ("Interlanguage errors" 2017).

This is because children mostly use one of them without knowing correct answer or not. In addition Overgeneralization creates mistakes because there are categorical exceptions. Learners use language in the wrong categories.

For example: foots instead of feet.

Furthermore, internal sequences also may cause errors by hearing a second language in different way. Children like imitating since they improve especially speaking skills by following teachers' and friends' pronunciation. However while studying at school variety of teachers teach them as a result some of them follow low experienced teachers and people as well ("International errors" 2017) Touchine (1986) informs that interlanguage and developmental errors happens because of difficulty of target language.

- Simplification: utilizing simple form rather than complex one
- Hypercorrection: teachers' zealous efforts to correct learners' errors
- Faulty teaching: caused by teacher, presentation orders, teaching materials
- Fossilization: some errors persist for a long time and getting rid of giving a sense of difficulty
- Avoidance: avoiding difficult syntactic structures
- False concept hypothesized: wrong concepts are formed about TL by learners.

Teachers play essential role to correct errors by affecting intelligibility and should concentrate on global errors more than local errors. Moreover, high frequency error like third person singular and irritating or stigmatizing errors should be directed to correct answer (Touchine, 1986)

Classification of Fossilization

Most researchers describe the fossilization period as a process of becoming stone and it may occur at different learning stages among age groups and different language levels.

Stigmatizing-irritating errors happen with pupils from lower socioeconomic classes who are very sensitive to ridicule about their informal variety of language.

Global errors-wrong word order in sentence: infers with communication and disturb the meaning of utterance.

Local errors- involve noun and verb inflections, use of article, preposition and auxiliaries.

Fossilization is persistent difficulty, cessation of learning, systematic use of erroneous forms, structural persistence etc. Mostly IL errors occur among adult learners because they learn it or continue learning after critical period and comparing to children they are less likely to achieve native like learners. Fossilization divided into two: temporary and permanent fossilization and it can also classified into individual and group fossilization (J.Yang.2002, Al-Khreshen, 2015, Tarone, 2006, 2018, Ipak, 2002). Yang (2002) claims that fossilization can be disappear but sometimes reappear and the phenomenon called back sliding. If learners with useful strategies know how to overcome errors and fossilization of interlanguage errors becomes weakening. Even children know experience them by behavioristic strategies. If IL errors do not take correctness and attention by learners or teachers frequently children's motivational intensity and desire to study TL are weakened and this will fossilize learners' errors and even limit their progress (Yang,2002).

Conclusion

Synthesized facts and theories proved that committing errors, mistakes is a normal process in some circumstances in order to gain data concerning second language learning and achieving native like speakers. However according to fossilization types: temporary fossilization shows that children and other learners may correct errors in a short period of time and Selinker suggested that it is a further development to target like forms. For correction of errors learners access their IL strategies, language transfer, IL communication strategies, overgeneralizing linguistic materials, behaviorism habits which children achieve and use mostly unconsciously and of course, teachers play important role by pointing mistakes and correcting them. Instead of having lack of analyzing ability with children, language acquisition device (LAD) are very high level in children and it helps easily overcome the difficulties by repeating through conversations, songs etc. But this kind of error reappearance is not considered real fossilization refers to as stabilization and if learners are in target language environment, their language competences easily overcome the difficulties in a short time. However even permanent fossilization may occur in all ages, if errors are not facilitated by learners or teachers. As a result, bad results lead learners especially children to ignorance of target language, stopping learning it and neglectful attitude. Attention should be equal for children in class since if low motivated learners do not accept care most times, without any doubt they confuse and

refuse the language and permanent fossilization happens with them. Teachers should be enthusiastic, responsible and should keep teaching interesting and original concepts to motivate learners for overcoming SL errors which cause difficulties. With respect to future research I suggest that placing greater emphasis on motivation and psychological structure for IL errors may yield further interesting, pedagogically useful results. Examining the patterns of motivation and psychological structure from sources may give another ways to overcome errors and finding out causes as well.

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